

YASHIL

**IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT**

*Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik,
ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*

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IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNING ROLI HAMDA
ISTIQBOLDAGI VAZIFALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI
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MUNDARIJA

1-SEKSIYA: BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI, IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	12
SUT YO'NALISHIDAGI QORAMOLCHILIKDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI HISOBI VA MAHSULOT TANNARXINI HISOBLASH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	13
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Karimov Ikrom, Abduganieva Dildora	
MEHNAT HAQI BO'YICHA MUOMALALARDA XATO, FIRIBGARLIK VA NOQONUNIY AMALLARNI SUD BUXGALTERIYA EKSPERTIZASI USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	17
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich	
G'ALLACHILIK KLASTERINING TASHKILY MEZONLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	20
Dusmuratov Radjabbay Davlatbaevich, Ilmuratov Shavkat Maxsumovich	
KORXONA TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALARI QADRSIZLANISHI AUDITNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	24
Urazov Komil Baxramovich, To'rayeva Farida Rustamovna	
AGROKLASTERLAR ICHKI SOTISH JARAYONIDA TRANSFERT BAHOLARNI BELGILASH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	28
Eshmuratov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
KONSOLIDASIYALASHGAN MOLIVYVIY HISOBOTLARNI TUZISHNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI ZARURATI.....	34
Avazov Iloxom Ravshanovich	
MOLIVYVIY HISOBOTNING BARQARORLIK STANDARTLARI	37
Kurbanov Ziyat Niyazovich	
ВВЕДЕНИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАТРАТ В СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ.....	41
Серекбаева Сауле Габитовна, Эшмуратов Улугбек Ташмуратович	
TOVAR-MODDIY QIYMATLIKLAR AUDITINI AUDITNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	46
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna	
AGROIQTISODIYOTNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA JORIY AKTIVLAR INVENTARIZATSIYASINI O'TKAZISH VA UNING TAHLILI USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	49
Ruziyeva Dilafruz Faxriddinovna	
INVESTITSYAVIY JOZIBADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITI VA UNI SHAKLLANTIRADIGAN OMILLAR.....	51
Abduganiyev Jahongir Behzod o'g'li, Eshmuratov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIK KORXONALARIDA ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBINING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	55
A.I.Alikulov, M.Sh.Baxriyev, M.N. Fayzullaev	
G'ALLACHILIK KLASTERLARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING XUSUSIYATLARI VA XORIJ TAJRIBALARI ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	59
Yuldashev Sherali Xaitovich, Xusanov Jaloliddin Xolmamat o'g'li, Tolibov Azamatjon Olimovich	
STRATEGIES FOR ADVANCING THE STANDARDS RELATED TO ACCOUNTING FOR FOREIGN EXCHANGE RATE FLUCTUATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN	63
Urazov K.B., Umarova Sh.K.	

BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARI HISOBI VA HISOBOTLARINI YURITISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	68
Nasim Boboev, Yorbekova Dilorom Muxammadqulovna, Umidullo Fayzullaev	
ASPECTS OF ACCOUNTING CONFIGURATION AND ORGANIZATION IN MODERN ECONOMIC SETTINGS.....	73
Hamdamova Guljahon Ablokulovna, Bahodirov Qosimxon Nasimxon o'g'li, Abdixalimov Nodirbek Abdumutal o'g'li	
ФИНАНСОВАЯ ГРАМОТНОСТЬ КЛИЕНТОВ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ В БАНКОВСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ	77
Нарзиева Гузаль Бахтиёровна	
BARQAROR O'SISH MAQSADLARIGA ERISHISHDA SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI VA UNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	81
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSİYALARNING AHAMIYATI.....	85
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna, Elmurodova Dilnoza Farxodovna, Rasulova Sevinch Shodiyor qizi	
THE ROLE OF INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL AUDIT IN STRENGTHENING CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN UZBEKISTAN	88
Urazov Komil Bahromovich, Oblokulov Sukhrob Usmon o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV HISOBI (O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MISOLIDA).....	90
Xamdamova Guljaxon Ablokulovna, Shakaraliyev Avazbek Xasan O'g'li, Daniyurov Xurshid Baxtiyrovich	
АДАПТАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВОГО УЧЕТА МНОГОПРОФИЛЬНЫХ ФЕРМЕРСКИХ ХОЗЯЙСТВ К МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫМ СТАНДАРТАМ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ	93
Ёрбекова Дилором Мухаммадқулловна, Асомиддинов Хусан Асомиддин угли, Мамадиёров Хусниддин Хасанович	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA INVENTARIZATSIYA NATIJALARI TAHLILINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	97
Ruziyeva Dilafuz Faxriddinovna	
ASALARICHILIK XO'JALIKLARIDA BIZNES JARAYONLARI HISOBINING NORMATIV-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	100
Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIK KORXONALARIDA ICHKI AUDITNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	107
Tilabov Shohruh Baxriddin o'g'li	
IQTISODIYOTNI JADAL RIVOJLANTIRISHGA QARATILGAN ISLOHOTLAR SHAROITIDA G'ALLACHILIK KLASTERLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ZARURATI, MOHIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	111
Yuldashev Sherali Xaitovich, Pardaboyev Asror O'lmas o'g'li	
AGROKLASTERLARDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR HISOBINI MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	115
Abdushukurov Xondamir Botiraliyevich, Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
BANK SEKTORINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI HAL QILISH YO'LLARI.....	120
Narziyeva Guzal Baxtiyrovna, Toshmurodova Dilbar Muzaffar qizi, Zarmaxmatov Nomozjon Boxodir o'g'li	
THE STATUS OF ACCOUNTING TODAY	123
Hamdamova Guljahon Ablokulovna, O'ktamov Nuriddin Abdumalik O'g'li, Raxmatullayev Abdullajon Murodullo O'g'li	
CHANGES IN THE STRUCTURE OF AGRICULTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	126
Yorbekova Dilorom Muxammadkulovna, Raxmatullayev Abdullajon Murodullo ugli	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MOSLASHTIRISH.....	130
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna, Abdurahmanova Jasmina Baxtiyorovna	
KORXONALARDA XARAJATLAR HISOBINING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI.....	133
Tilabov Shohruh Baxriddin o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIK KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH JARAYONLARI.....	137
Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich, Rasulberdiyev G'ayratjon Sharof o'g'li, Xusanov Shohjahon Shavxidin o'g'li, Rustamova Dildora Dunyodjon qizi	
BUDJET HISOBINING IQTISODIYOTIMIZDA TUTGAN O'RNI VA UNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.....	143
Tuxtayev Zafar Mamatkulovich	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA ASOSIY VOSITALARNING TASHKILY-USLUBIY ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	147
Fayzullayev Murodbek Nematullayevich, Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich	
2-SEKSIYA: INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AGRAR IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA UNING YECHIMLARI.....	151
KAMBAG'ALLIK MUAMMOSI, UNI BARTARAF ETISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI VA HOZIRGI HOLATI.....	152
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Aslonov Xotamjon Sharifboy o'g'li, Esirgapov Diyor Akramovich	
BULUTLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA SOLIQ HISOBOTI TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	157
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT” GA O'TISH ZARURIYATI VA UNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	162
Olmasov Umidjon G'iyosovich, Salamov Ibroxim, Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA CHORVACHILIK SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	168
Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AGRAR IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA UNING YECHIMLARI.....	172
Ruziyeva Dilafruz Faxriddinovna	
“OZIQ-OVQAT ISROFI VA U BILAN KURASHISH STRATEGIYALARI”.....	176
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Abduqahhorov Najmiddin Sayfiddin o'g'li, Vaslidinov Behruz Vaslidinovich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AHOLINING IQTISODIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	182
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AGRAR IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA UNING YECHIMLARI.....	185
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Azimjon Baxodirov, Ilhom Mamatqulov	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI QISHLOQ JOYLARIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	190
Xamdanova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Boyjigitov Kamronbekmirzo Sobirjon o'g'li, Baxriddinov Abubakir Oloviddin o'g'li	
IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KICHIK BIZNESNING ROLINI OSHIRISH.....	195
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Ollonazarova Mavlyuda Shixnazar qizi	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISHDA ELEKTRON TIJORATNI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	199
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna, Safarova Baxora Aslamovna, Bozorova Beg'ubor Tolib qizi, Murodqulova Mexrangiz Dilshodovna, Avazboyeva Ruxshona Azizovna	

CHORVACHILIKDA VETERINARIYA XIZMATLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	202
Eshanqulov Sirojiddin Xakimovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA LOGISTIK MARKAZLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING HOLATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	206
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Tursunaliyev Abdulaziz Shokirjon o'g'li, Toshniyozov Anvarbek Alisher o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH: KELAJAK TEXNOLOGIYALARI	211
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Bilolbek Quvonchbek o'g'li Boytemirov	
XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MUHIM OMILLARI	215
Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Iymonqulova Mavluda O'rozali qizi, Raxmonberdiyev Sherzod Alisher o'g'li	
ЗАНЯТОСТЬ И СОКРОЩЕНИЕ БЕЗРОБОТИЦЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	219
Назарова М.Ш., Бердикулов Р.А.	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARI SAVDOSINING RIVOJLANISH EVOLYUTSIYASI.....	226
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”NI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULKNING AHAMIYATI	230
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Dilmurabonu Faruxovna Amrillayeva, Muqaddas Muxamadaliyevna Xusenova	
UZUMCHILIK TARMOG'IDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA ERISHISHDA SUVDAN TEJAMKORLIK BILAN FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI.....	235
Salamov Ibroxim, Jonibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich	
QISHLOQ HUDUDIDA KICHIK BIZNES SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	239
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna	
BOZOR IQTISODIYOTIDA MULKCHILIK MUNOSABATLARINI AMALGA OSHIRISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	243
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Muqaddas Muxamadaliyevna Xusenova, Dilmurabonu Faruxovna Amrillayeva	
GLOBAL BIZNESDA STRATEGIK YONDASHUVLAR.....	247
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna, Umrzoqov Adxam, Mirzabayev Shoxruhjon Orzumurodovich, Saidmurodov Sardor Mirsalohovich	
TADBIRKORLIKNI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO'LLAB-QUVATLASH TIZIMI TAHLILI	251
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Ibragimov Jahongir Ilhom o'g'li, IbragimovBotir Uktambov o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING TASHQI SAVDO SIYOSATI.....	257
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Inomjon Rustam o'g'li Xo'jaqulov, Sherzod Mexriddinovich Raxmatullayev	
THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF ACCELERATED DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN A MODERN MARKET ECONOMY	262
Khamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Rasulberdiyev G'ayratjon Sharof o'g'li, Ro'zmatov Feruzbek Inoyat o'g'li	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT” TAMOYILLARINI AMALGA OSHIRISHDAGI ASOSIY VAZIFALAR	265
Xudoyberdiyev.U.X., Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
YOSHLAR ORASIDA KICHIK BIZNES SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	268
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Ollonazarova Mavlyuda Shixnazar qizi	
O'TISH DAVRIDAGI IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK KORXONALARNING LOGISTIKA TIZIMI	273
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Islomjon Jamshedovich Jamshedov	
GLOBAL ISISH SABABLARI VA UNING IQTISODIY OQIBATLARI.....	278
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi, Boyjigitov Kamronbekmirzo Sobirjon o'g'li, Mirzabayev Shoxruhjon Orzumurodovich, Saidmurodov Sardor Mirsalohovich	
SERVIS XIZMATI KO'RSATISHDA CHO'L-YAYLOV CHORVACHILIGI MAHSULOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	282
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Hotamov Adhamjon Asqarjon o'g'li	

AGROTURIZMNING YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDAGI O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI: O‘ZBEKISTON UCHUN XORIJIY TAJRIBA ASOSIDA TAKLIFLAR.....	287
Ergashboyev Minghojiddin Jasurbek o‘g‘li, Yuldoshev Husniddin To‘lqin o‘g‘li, Eshmuradov Ulug‘bek Tashmuratovich	
“YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISH ORQALI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	293
Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich	
PARRANDA TUXUMINI YETISHTIRISHDA EKOLOGIK MUHITNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHGA TA‘SIRI.....	297
Vaslidinov Bexruz Vaslidinovich, Salamov Ibrohim, Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULKDAN FOYDALANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	302
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Sherzod Mexriddinovich Raxmatullayev, Inomjon Rustam o‘g‘li Xo‘jaqulov	
CHO‘L-YAYLOV CHORVACHILIGI MAHSULOTLARI SOTISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA TARMOQNI MODERINIZATSIYALASH	308
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Hotamov Adhamjon Asqarjon o‘g‘li	
IQTISODIY TENGSIZLIK VA U BILAN KURASHISH USULLARI.....	313
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi, Mahammadahliyev Muhammadkarim, Abduzoirov Sarvarbek Sanjar o‘g‘li, Jumayev Azamat Uchqun o‘g‘li	
“YASHIL” IQTISODIYOT VA UNING O‘ZBEKISTONDA BANDLIKKA TA‘SIRI.....	316
Nazarova M.Sh., Berdiqulov R.A.	
SAMARQAND VILOYATIDA AGROTURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	322
Jo‘raqul Rahmiddin o‘g‘li Yaxshiliqo, Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA “YASHIL”IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKLLANTIRISH, RIVOJLANTIRISH VAZIFALARI VA BOSQICHLARI	327
Maryam Sharipovna Nazarova, Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashev, Azimjon Baxodirov Ilhom Mamatqulov, Ilhom Mamatqulov	
QISHLOQDA YASHOVCHI AYOLLAR – MEHNAT RESURSLARINING ISHSIZLIK MASALALARI	332
Murtazayev Olim, Murtazayev Akbarxon Olimovich	
XXI-ASRDA SHAKLLANGAN YANGI IQTISODIYOTLAR TARKIBIDA KREATIV IQTISODIYOT PRINSIPLARI VA TURLARINING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	336
Mamayunus Pardayev, Obid Pardayev	
ISHSIZLIKNING ZAMONAVIY SHAKLLARI VA BANDLIKNI OSHIRISHDA STRATEGIK YONDASHUVLAR.....	340
Navruzbek Azimjonovich Rajabov, Safarova Bahora Aslamovna	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MEHNAT BOZORI TRANSFORMATSIYASINING YANGI TALABLAR DOIRASIDA TAKOMILLASHUVI	344
Pardayev Mamayunus Qarshibayevich, Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna, Babanazarova Sevara Abdunazarovna	
YANGI O‘ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA XIZMAT KO‘RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI KAMBAG‘ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH MUHIM VA DOLZARB MASALALARDAN BIRIDIR	348
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzokovich, Mirzayev A	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA AGROTURIZM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	352
Ergashboyev Minghojiddin Jasurbek o‘g‘li, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich	
XO‘JALIK YURITUVCHI SubyektLARDA INSON RESURSLARINI BAHOLASH VA TAHLILIGA NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR	358
Pardayev Mamayunus Qarshiboyevich, Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusova, Babanazarova Sevara Abdunazarovna, Mamayunusov Temur Olimovich	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA EKOLOGIK TA'LIM VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH CHORA-TADBIRLARI.....	362
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi, Abduzoirov Sarvarbek Sanjar o'g'li, Solayev Sanjar Hamdam o'g'li	
MEHNAT BOZORI TRANSFORMATSIYASIDA ZAMONAVIY TALABLARDAN KELIB CHIQADIGAN YONDOSHUVLAR.....	365
Pardayev Mamayunus Qarshibayevich, Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna, Mamayunusov Temur Olimovich	
3-SEKSIYA: QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH: KELAJAK TEXNOLOGIYALARI.....	369
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА: ТЕХНОЛОГИИ БУДУЩЕГО.....	370
Muxamediyeva Dilnoz Tulkuinovna, Saфарова Лола Улмасовна	
IQTISODIY-MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISH: MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK KLASTERLARI EKIN MAYDONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	374
Urdushev Xamrakul, Sirojiddin Eshanqulov	
BOG'DORCHILIK TARMOG'INING HOLATI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH TENDENSIYALARINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI	379
Akbarov Husan O'zbekxonovich, Urdushev Xamrakul, Jalilov Shoxrux Zafar o'g'li	
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: IMPORTANCE, DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION	383
Koshkaldal Iryna, Celms Armands, Gurskiene Virginija, Dombrovska Olena	
О МЕТОДИКЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ РЕШЕНИЮ МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИХ ГОЛОВЛОМОК НА УРОКАХ МАТЕМАТИКИ	386
Aktamova Vasila Ukatamovna, Ahtamova Z.U., Muradova Mexribon Sobirovna	
FIZIKA FANINING O'ZBEKISTON AGRAR IQTISODIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLARINI HAL ETISHDAGI POTENTIALI.....	393
R. Berdiyev, U. E. Nurimov, B. U. Amonov	
FIZIKA FANINI INTERNET TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANIB O'QITISH	397
Raximov O., Mamatkulov	
CHORVACHILIK XO'JALIKLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI TASHKIL ETISHDA KO'P OMILLI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH USULLARI.....	401
Mavlyanov Majid Tuychievich	
AYRIM IQTISODIY MASALALARNI YECHISHDA TAQRIBIY SONLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	406
Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna, Bozorboyev Komiljon Shuxrat o'g'li, Eshdavlratov Samandar Otabek o'g'li, G'aniyev Anvar Maqsud o'g'li	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ КОМПЛЕКСНЫХ ЧИСЕЛ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГЕОМЕТРИИ	410
Aktamova Vasila Ukatamovna, Ahtamova Umida Ukatamovna, Mayramaliyeva Dilbar Eldorovna	
MEVA VA SABZOVOTLARNI FIZIKAVIY USULDA QAYTA ISHLASH TEXNALOGIYASI.....	417
N.Mamatkulov., M.Raxmatov., R.Berdiyev	
BEGONA O'TLAR VA ZARARKUNANDALARGA QARSHI KURASHDA ROBOTOTEXNIKA	421
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich, Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna, Usanov Yoqub Dilmurod o'g'li	
AQLLI SUG'ORISH TIZIMLARI YORDAMIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI.....	425
Sulaymonov Mirobid Abdulkolich	
SMART TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARINI SOTISH: BLOCKCHAIN TEXNOLOGIYASINING QO'LLANILISHI	342
Aktamova Vasila Ukatamovna	

RAQAMLI TAHLIL YORDAMIDA O‘SIMLIKLAR UCHUN OPTIMAL O‘SISH SHAROITLARINI YARATISH	436
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich, Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna, Jumayev Azamat Uchqun o‘g‘li, Hamdullayev Jamoliddin Feruzxon o‘g‘li	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA RAQAMLI TEXNALOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	440
N.Mamatkulov, R.Aminov	
UY HAYVONLARINI RO‘YXATDAN O‘TKAZISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA ULARNING QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDAGI IJTIMOYIY VA IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	443
Sulaymonov Miroid Abdusolikhovich, Usanov Rashid Sharofovich	
ISSIQXONALARNING REAL VAQT REJIMIDA BOSHQARUV MONITORING TIZIMINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH, NAZORAT QILISH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	448
Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna	
RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA EKOLOGIK INNOVATSIYALAR ORQALI O‘ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI JORIY ETISH.....	454
Usanov Rashid Sharofovich	
ZARARKUNANDALAR TARQALISHINI BASHORAT QILISHDA SUN‘IY INTELLEKT MODELLARI.	458
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich, Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI YERLARINI GEOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING AMALIY YONDASHUVI.....	462
Xaknazarova Xurshidabonu Kenjayevna	
FLUTTER ASOSIDAGI O‘SIMLIKLARNI TANISH VA SOG‘LOMLIGINI TAHLIL QILISH	467
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich	
FERMERLAR UCHUN MOBIL ILOVALAR: AXBOROT, TAHLIL VA MASLAHATLAR.....	471
Aktamova Vasila Uktamovna, Axtamova Umida Uktamovna	
IOT VA AI INTEGRATSIYASI ORQALI SUVNI TEJASH	475
Raxmatullayeva Nozima Shodiqulovna	

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF ACCELERATED DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN A MODERN MARKET ECONOMY

Khamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna

Assistant of the Department of Economics and Menejment,
Samarkand State University veterinary medicine,
livestock and biotechnologies;

Rasulberdiyev G'ayratjon Sharof o'g'li

Student of the Department of Economics and Accounting,
Samarkand State University veterinary medicine,
livestock and biotechnologies;

Ro'zmatov Feruzbek Inoyat o'g'li

Student of the Department of Economics and Accounting,
Samarkand State University veterinary medicine,
livestock and biotechnologies

Annotatsiya: This study examines the challenges faced by the rural labor force, focusing on labor productivity reserves in the rural labor market using agricultural enterprises as a case study. The paper highlights the persistent presence of job vacancies in rural areas that often go unfilled due to comparatively lower wage levels in rural sectors and the national economy overall.

Kalit so'zlar: Service essence, real services, ideal services, service development in practice, transformation of the service sector, labor force structure, employment, unemployment rate, labor productivity, agricultural production.

Abstract: Ushbu tadqiqotda qishloq mehnat bozori misolida mehnat unumdorligini oshirish zaxiralari hamda qishloq mehnat kuchi duch kelayotgan muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada qishloq hududlarida bo'sh ish o'rinlarining mavjudligiga qaramay, ularning ko'pincha to'ldirilmasligining asosiy sababi sifatida qishloq xo'jaligi sohasida va umuman milliy iqtisodiyotda nisbatan past ish haqi darajasi ko'rsatilgan.

Key words: xizmat mohiyati, real xizmatlar, ideal xizmatlar, amaliyotda xizmatlar rivoji, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining transformatsiyasi, mehnat kuchi tarkibi, bandlik, ishsizlik darajasi, mehnat unumdorligi, qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishi.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются проблемы, с которыми сталкивается сельская рабочая сила, с акцентом на резервы повышения производительности труда на сельском рынке труда на примере сельскохозяйственных предприятий. В статье подчёркивается наличие постоянных вакансий в сельской местности, которые часто остаются незаполненными из-за относительно низкого уровня заработной платы в сельском секторе и в национальной экономике в целом.

Ключевые слова: сущность услуги, реальные услуги, идеальные услуги, развитие услуг на практике, трансформация сферы услуг, структура рабочей силы, занятость, уровень безработицы, производительность труда, сельскохозяйственное производство.

Introduction

The socio-economic essence of the Institute of Services. The socio-economic importance of the service sector can also be understood from the fact that, in recent years, it has been developed through digital economy innovations and services implemented in line with current requirements, based on achieving savings among the subjects of the industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at improving efficiency.

The development of the service sector and the improvement of the standard of living of the population require the formulation of long-term performance indicators. This creates opportunities for the development of conceptual directions and programs for the service sector in our Republic. This, in turn, requires the creation of opportunities to increase employment through the expansion of the service sector. [1]

Socio-economic efficiency in the development of the sector reveals a number of interrelated and complementary issues. Achieving social efficiency based on people's living conditions, employment, and services offered in recreational processes applies not only to services rendered but also to real sectors that produce material goods. In both areas, labor productivity – which underpins economic efficiency – provides the basis for growth. Economic efficiency and labor productivity, along with the stable increase in the volume and quality of material assets, create all the necessary conditions for the population and serve as a material basis for developing support mechanisms.

However, for real sectors as well as the service sector, in evaluating the activities of economic entities and specific labor teams, it is necessary to consider their peculiarities. For example, in the service sector – particularly tourism, education and culture, healthcare, housing, and communal services – not only is the standard and quality of life shaped, but the consumption of domestically produced goods is also influenced, thus impacting the real sector and the economy as a whole. Even today, in the context of a pandemic, the standard and quality of life of the population further increase the social importance of service provision.

Therefore, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Program for the Development of the Service Sector in 2016–2020” made a decision to address exactly these problems, which is of particular importance due to its dedication. It contains:

- development of engineering, communication, automotive, and transport service infrastructure through the introduction of modern information and communication technologies and implementation of structural changes in networks;

- formation of a competitive environment, and support for the development of small and private entrepreneurship;

- expansion of various service types, including new communication facilities;

- provision of access for the population to telecommunications networks, enabling high-quality services, digital telephone communications, and television transitions;

- development of financial services through the introduction of modern electronic payment technologies;

- implementation of measures for the further development of high-tech medical services.

Ensuring that the above priorities are carried out in the context of the digital economy requires improvements in investment policies and mechanisms, the development of organizational measures, structural management, and operations. During a period of socio-political change, it assumes the legal independence, protection, and efficiency of established market entities, as well as increased activity at both local and regional levels.

Another important socio-economic role of the service sector in our country is that it determines the strategy for industrial-innovative development of the economy based on digital technologies. After all, the reorganization of the industry and allocation of credit resources to develop technological equipment for enterprises must be aligned with their needs. At the same time, diversification opens up new economic opportunities.

Another important socio-economic significance of the rapid development of the service sector is explained by the specification of material, technical, and financial resources provided for its development. First, the state facilitates the development of the service sector through the allocation of preferential loans; second, the level of development of services reflects the socio-economic condition of the country; third, service development focuses on social protection through targeted loans and contributes significantly to employment.

A key feature of how labor resources are used is work efficiency. As an economic category, it reflects the cost-effectiveness of living labor in purposeful activity. The productivity of agricultural labor generally depends on the availability, skill level, and degree of utilization of labor resources. The labor force is defined as the population of a country within the legally prescribed working age, capable of working and ready for socially useful activities in various spheres of the national economy [6].

The workforce of agricultural enterprises includes permanent, seasonal, and temporary workers, as well as other categories of employees. It is necessary to distinguish between the total number of employees of agricultural enterprises and those directly involved in agricultural production (crop production and animal husbandry). Some agricultural workers are employed in other sectors of the economy, such as construction, industry, housing, cultural, and consumer services [5].

In rural areas, there are vacancies in the labor market, but they are not always in demand, as there are various reasons that encourage a rural resident to make a decision about employment, the main of which is a decent wage level, and, as you know, wages in rural areas are the lowest compared to other sectors of the economy [3].

In the countryside, where agricultural production occupies an important place in the employment of the population, climatic conditions and the level of production development are of great importance. An equally important condition in this case is the quality of labor potential and the profitability of labor. These factors determine the socio-economic situation in the formation of employment in a particular territory. The stable development of real sector industries in the region creates the necessary jobs, provides employment and incomes for the rural population.

The dynamics of economic inequality between rural and urban residents in terms of wage income continues to deepen. Changes in the incomes of the population and the stratification of society lead to the most negative consequences, because increasing inequality in the distribution of income and their low level among the majority of the population lowers aggregate consumer demand, making it one-sided, which does not contribute to the development of social production and the real sector of the economy. The jobs where the largest number of people employed in the region's economy are concentrated are low profitable. This fact pushes employees to look for additional work. Currently, wages in agriculture do not perform either a reproductive or stimulating function to the required extent. Due to weak incentives, workers do not seek to increase their labor activity in public production. The able-bodied population is looking for additional sources of income in the form of additional employment. Since the labor market in rural areas is monopolized by agricultural enterprises, and in some areas there are no employers at all. The flow of labor takes place towards personal subsidiary farms, where employment, due to the use of agricultural enterprises, sometimes brings even more income than pay in public enterprises.

Therefore, we have identified the main problems of the rural labor market: the outflow of labor resources from rural areas, and especially young people, low wages, poor awareness of rural residents about government programs. In turn, government support for rural areas will help develop the labor potential of this segment of the labor market.

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El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

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